

TABLE-1. SEDIMENTATION COEFFICIENT AND RELATIVE VISCOSITY OF CELULOSE TRINITRATE IN ACETONE.

Concentration gms/dl.	$S_{20,w} \times 10^{13}$	$\eta_r = \eta/\eta_0$	$\frac{1}{S_{20,w}} - K'_{s,c} \times c^2$	$S_{20,w} \times C$	$S_{20,w} \times \eta_r$
0.2955	2.178	9.443	0.4614	0.6436	20.57
0.2396	2.392	6.200	0.4195	0.5732	14.84
0.1977	2.734	4.350	0.3668	0.5405	11.90
0.1508	3.054	2.886	0.3281	0.4606	8.81
0.1044	3.505	2.048	0.2856	0.3659	7.18

values at higher concentrations. However, at lower concentrations, the corrections were very low at the lower percentages of relative viscosities.

The Burgers' equation and the Newman-Loeb relation when applied to the present system, resulted in very good linear plots and the values obtained by extrapolation to infinite dilution were found to be in good agreement. The plots are shown in figs. (2) and (3).

Fig. 2 Plot of $S_{20,w}$ vs $S_{20,w} \times c$ for Cellulose trinitrate in acetone.

Fig. 3 Plot of $(\frac{1}{S_{20,w}} - K'_{s,c} \times c^2)$ vs c for Cellulose trinitrate in acetone.

TABLE-2. SEDIMENTATION COEFFICIENT AND RELATIVE VISCOSITY OF CELLULOSE TRINITRATE IN ETHYL ACETATE.

0.2180	2.178	9.642	0.4558	0.4749	21.00
0.1665	2.500	6.269	0.3981	0.4162	15.67
0.1396	2.756	4.737	0.3614	0.3847	13.05
0.1230	2.712	3.856	0.3676	0.3329	10.46
0.0786	3.251	2.327	0.3072	0.2555	7.56

The values of sedimentation coefficients obtained in ethyl acetate and acetone do not show a pronounced difference. It is expected that the sedimentation coefficient will depend on the viscosity of the medium, more resistance to the flow of the solute molecules will be offered in a medium in which the viscosity is higher. The data in tables 1 and 2 fulfil this expectation.

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Chemical Investigation of *Rumex dentatus* Linn

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RUMEX dentatus Linn. (Polygonaceae) commonly grows as an annual herb in Bundelkhand, gangetic plains and the sub-Himalayan tract upto 1000'. The plant is highly toxic to livestock causing 'diarrhoea and dermatitis¹⁻³'. No reference on its components is available in the literature, although, sister species³⁻⁶

have been chemically investigated. In view of the toxic nature of the plant, studies were undertaken on its chemical constituents and the presence of myricyl alcohol, β -D-glucoside of β -sitosterol, free β -sitosterol, emodin, aloe-emodin and quercetin is reported here.

Experimental

Powdered plant material (1.2 kg) was extracted with alcohol (95%) by percolation at room temperature. The alcoholic extractive was separated into petroleum ether (40-60°) and benzene soluble fractions. These fractions were chromatographed separately on Brockman's neutral alumina and silica-gel columns, respectively. Elution of the columns with different solvents and their mixtures yielded the following crystalline compounds.

Petroleum Ether extract :

Myricyl alcohol—Eluted with petroleum ether and crystallized from benzene, as colourless microcrystalline compound (260 mg), m.p. and mixed m.p. (with an authentic sample) 85–87°, $(\alpha)_D^{20} \pm 0^\circ$ (CHCl_3 , c 1.3%) IR: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3460 cm^{-1} and formed a monoacetate m.p. 70-71°.

β -sitosterol—(Pet. ether: benzene, 1:1). It crystallised from acetone (charcoal) as colourless needles (650 mg) m.p. 136-37°, $(\alpha)_D^{20} -33^\circ$ (CHCl_3 , c 1%) and showed positive tests for sterol: IR : $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3420, 2920, 1470, 1370, 1055, 1030, 810 cm^{-1} . It formed an acetate m.p. 128-29° $(\alpha)_D^{20} -37^\circ$ (CHCl_3 , c 1.2%) and was identified as β -sitosterol in the usual way.

β -D-glucoside of β -sitosterol δ : (ethyl acetate : ethanol :: 1:9). It crystallised from excess of ethanol (charcoal) as colourless crystalline product (430 mg) m.p. 270°-72°, IR : $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3500, 2980, 2930, 1460, 1385, 1370, 1060 cm^{-1} and gave positive L-B and Molisch's tests. It formed an acetate (acetic anhydride and sodium acetate fused) m.p. 170°. On hydrolysis (alcoholic HCl 7%, 5 hr), it yielded β -sitosterol and glucose (paper co-chromatography) in two solvent systems butanol : acetic acid : water :: 4 : 1 : 5 and butanol : pyridine : water :: 3 : 1.5 : 1 using aniline phthalate as detecting reagent). Mixed m.p. with authentic β -D-glucoside of β -sitosterol was not depressed.

Benzene extract :

Emodin—eluted with acetone and crystallised from ethanol as orange yellow needles (120 mg) m.p. 259-60°. It gave magenta colour with concentrated sulphuric acid and cherry red colour with aqueous alkali solution characteristic of emodin: IR : $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3390, 2930, 1675, 1630, 1570, 1040, 768, 730 cm^{-1} . The compound was identified as emodin by its direct comparison with an authentic sample.

Aloe-emodin (acetone-alcohol, 1:1) was obtained as orange yellow crystalline product (65 mg) m.p. 222-23°.

Remaining alcoholic extractive was hydrolysed with alcoholic hydrochloric acid (7%, 3 hr). On extraction with ether, it gave a yellow product, which crystallized from acetone: methanol (1:1) mixture as yellow needles (170 mg) m.p. 310-312°. The compound answered tests for flavonols and formed an acetate (acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate) m.p. 194-95°. Identity of the compound with quercetin was confirmed by paper chromatography in two solvent systems (butanol: acetic acid: water :: 4 : 1 : 5 and butanol saturated with water), mixed m.p. determination and spectral data.

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Complexes of Copper(II) with Ethyl- β -Arylaminoacronates

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ETHYL- β -arylaminoacronates are bidentate and get coordinated to copper from C=N nitrogen and C=O oxygen, the other two positions being linked to two halogens giving a six membered ring complex :

Such copper complexes are more stable towards water and sodium carbonate and have lower melting points when compared with zinc, cadmium and mercuric chloride complexes which decompose on air exposure¹; while the former darken on light exposure